

Occurrence of Vancomycin Resistant Enterococci in Chicken Flocks

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Abstract

Enterococci are normal inhabitants of the gastrointestinal tract of humans and animal; found in soil, water, and food. The current study aimed to determine the occurrence and antibiotic resistance pattern profile of some *Enterococcus spp.* isolates from chicken. A total of 300 cloacal swabs were collected from 12 chicken flocks including, Saso, broilers and breeder flocks (100 samples per each) from El Fayoum and BeniSuef Governorates, Egypt. The obtained results clarified that the overall isolation rate of Enterococci in examined chicken flocks was 46%, while it was 13, 16 and 17% in broilers, sasso and layers flocks, respectively. In addition, it was found that all the examined Enterococci isolates were positive for both 16S rRNA of Enterococcus and *E. faecalis*, while only 8 isolates were found to be positive for presence of *vanA gene* representative for Vancomycin resistant Enterococci by PCR. Finally, it was concluded that the vancomycin resistant *E. faecalis* constitutes one of the most predominant Enterococcus species among chicken. Thus, the prevention and control programs of Enterococcus should be focused to control these species.

Key words: *E. faecalis*, Vancomycin, Enterococci, Chicken, PCR

Introduction:

Enterococci are normal gastrointestinal inhabitants of humans and animals. They are enteric streptococci but differ from the streptococcus species in two important respects that; they tolerate NaCl 6.5% as well as bile salts; so, they can grow on MacConkey agar as red, pin-point colonies and some isolates are motile. Enterococci are non-motile, Gram-positive, facultative anaerobic catalase-negative

coccioid bacteria that appear singly, in pairs, or in short chains on stained smears (Arias and Murray, 2012). For many years, they were considered as normal flora and non-harmful to man (Wierzchowska et al., 2012). However, over the last years, enterococci have emerged as major nosocomial pathogens, representing an increasingly important problem for public health (Sood et al., 2008 and Zhou et al., 2020). Occasionally, Enterococcus infection

among chicken is a leading cause of many clinical diseases including lameness and respiratory diseases. Enterococcus infections are widespread worldwide. Enterococci categorized as the third cause of bacteremia in Europe and in America accounting for approximately 11%–13% of all bacteremia cases (**Ammerlaan et al., 2013**). Among all recognized Enterococci species, only a few species are isolated from birds, mainly: *E. faecalis*, *E. faecium*, *E. hirae*, *E. cecorum*, *E. durans*, *E. avium*, *E. casseliflavus*, *E. gallinarum*, *E. raffinosus* and *E. columbae* (**Dolka et al., 2016**). Enterococci are intrinsically resistant to various antimicrobial classes and there are remarkable differences in the patterns and to a lesser extent in the genetic bases of acquired resistance between *E. faecium* and *E. faecalis* (**Arias and Murray 2012**). Dissemination of vancomycin resistance Enterococci (VRE) can occur through horizontal transmission of resistant genes which can be transferred to Enterococci by plasmids (**Handwerger et al., 1995**). VREs are categorized according to the expression of vancomycin resistance genes to the *van A*, *van B*, or *van C*, *van D*, *van E* and *van G* phenotypes, as well as the emerging and the transmission of the antibiotic resistance genotype (**Facklam et al., 2002**). Enterococci can cause severe

clinical diseases in chicken by acquiring pathogenic factors. In this case, Enterococci could be changed from opportunistic or normal inhabitants to pathogenic. These virulence factors enable the infecting Enterococci strains to colonize and invade the host tissue and to translocate through epithelial cells and evade the host's immune response (**Johnson 1994**). There are many virulence genes of Enterococcus species such as ace (collagen binding cell wall protein), agg (aggregative pheromone-inducing adherence to extra-matrix protein), esp (enterococcal surface protein), hyl (hyaluronidase), cylA (hemolysin), and gelE (gelatinase) (**Klibi et al., 2007**). Nucleic acid-based tests using PCR are increasingly being used in laboratories to replace time-consuming, labor intensive and less sensitive conventional microbiological and disc diffusion methods for the detection of antibiotic resistance. Various PCR methods have been developed to identify the Enterococcus genus, VRE genes and virulence factors of Enterococcus spp (**Jackson et al., 2004**). Sequencing data of 16SrRNA gene of Enterococci are important to determine the relationship of clinically relevant Enterococcus species. The 16SrRNA sequencing is the gold standard for microbial identification. More definitive

delineation of the genus *Enterococcus*, comparative 16 SrRNA sequence analysis can distinguish between several 'species groups' within the genus and can determine the relation between isolates from different sources (Willems and Van Schaik, 2009 and Rosema et al., 2018). Currently, it is not fully elucidated whether the avian *Enterococcus* infections can be a reservoir for zoonotic infections of human with multidrug resistant *Enterococcus*. Therefore, there is a crucial need to improve our understanding of the veterinary epidemiology of this potential zoonotic pathogen. So, the current study aimed to determine the occurrence of *Enterococcus* species infections among chicken flocks to determine the antibiotic resistance pattern profile of some *Enterococcus spp.* isolates from chicken.

Material and Methods

Sample collection: A total of 300 cloacal swabs were collected from 12 chicken flocks including, Saso, broilers and breeder flocks (100 samples per each). All chicken samples were collected from El Fayoum and BeniSuef Governorates, Egypt and transported quickly under shelling conditions to the laboratory of Microbiology of Cairo University.

Bacterial isolation and biochemical identification: Isolation and identifications

of *Enterococcus spp.* were performed following the protocols of Facklam et al., (2002). Samples were pre-enriched on brain heart infusion broth (Oxoid) and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. A loopful from the pre-enriched samples was streaked on the Bile Esculin Azide agar (Oxoid) with addition of Cefotax antibiotic and incubated at 37 °C for 24 – 48 hours under microaerophilic conditions. Trypticase Soya Agar (Difco) and nutrient agar media were used for purification and preservations of the suspected *Enterococcus spp.* isolates. Colonies suspected to be *Enterococcus* were subjected to identification tests using the following characteristics: growth and hydrolysis of bile-esculin agar, absence of catalase and fermentation of sucrose as well as motility and pigmentation. Species identifications were confirmed by PCR using specific primers.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Tests: It was performed by using Muller Hinton agar medium (HI media, India). Standard agar disk diffusion method was employed according to the recommendations of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), (2012) using commercial antibiotic disks (Oxoid). The used antibiotic discs were Amoxicillin/clavulanate (AMC) (30 µg), Erythromycin E (15 µg),

Trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole (SXT) (25 µg), Ciprofloxacin (CIP) (5 µg), Streptomycin (S) (10 µg), Vancomycin (VA) (30 µg), Penicillin (Pen) (10 µg), Linezolid (LZD) (2 µg), Gentamicin (CN) (10 µg), Chloramphenicol (C) (30 µg), Rifampin (RA) (5 µg).

Molecular characterization of Enterococci, *E. faecalis* and detection of Van A resistance gene by Polymerase Chain Reaction: All molecular reactions were performed at the Central Laboratory, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Cairo University. Twenty isolates of *E. faecalis* were further investigated by PCR for presence of *16S rRNA* and *Van A*.

Extraction of DNA using QIAamp DNA Mini Kit (Catalogue No.51304): The QIAamp DNA Mini Kit provides silica-membrane-based nucleic acid purification from different types of samples. The spin-column procedure does not require

mechanical homogenization, so total hands-on preparation time is only 20 minutes.

Oligonucleotide primers (Midland Certified Reagent Company Oilgos, USA): were listed in Table (1).

Cycling conditions of the primers during PCR: Temperature and time conditions of the primers during PCR are shown in Table (2) according to Emerald Amp GT PCR Mastermix (Takara) kit.

Agarose gel electrophoresis was carried out according to Sambrook *et al.*, (1989) with modification: Twenty µl of each PCR product samples, negative control and positive control were loaded to the gel. The power supply was 1-5 volts/cm of the tank length. The run was stopped after about 30 minutes and the gel were transferred to UV cabinet. The gel was photographed by a gel documentation system and the data was analyzed through computer software.

Table 1. Oligonucleotide primers:

Agent	Gene	Primer Sequence 5'-3'	Amplified product	Reference
Enterococcus	<i>16S rRNA</i>	ATCAGAGGGGGATAACACTT	337 bp	Matsuda <i>et al.</i>, 2009
		ACTCTCATCCTTGTCTTCTC		
<i>E. faecalis</i>	<i>16S rRNA</i>	GTT TAT GCC GCA TGG CAT AAGAG	310 bp	Zoletti <i>et al.</i>, 2006
		CCG TCA GGG GAC GTT CAG		
Enterococcus	<i>vanA</i>	CATGACGTATCGGTA AAAATC	885 bp	Patel <i>et al.</i>, 1997
		ACCGGGCAGRGTATTGAC		

Table 2. Cycling conditions of the primers during PCR:

Agent	Gene	Primary denaturation	Secondary denaturation	Annealing	Extension	No. of cycles	Final extension
Enterococcus	<i>16S rRNA</i>	94°C 5 min.	94°C 30 sec.	50°C 45 sec.	72°C 45 sec.	35	72°C 10 min.
<i>E. faecalis</i>	<i>16S rRNA</i>	94°C 5 min.	94°C 30 sec.	50°C 30 sec.	72°C 30 sec.		72°C 7 min.
Enterococcus	<i>vanA</i>	94°C 5 min.	94°C 30 sec.	50°C 45 sec.	72°C 50 sec.		72°C 10 min.

Results

The recorded data in **Table (3)** clarified that the incidence rate of enterococci in examined chicken flocks was 13, 16 and 17% in broilers, sasso and layers flocks, respectively. Enterococci reveals Gram-positive, facultative anaerobic catalase-negative coccoid bacteria that appear singly, in pairs, or in short chains on stained smears; red, pin-point colonies on MacConkey agar and positive bile esculin (Fig. 1). Antibiotic

profile reveals 8 isolates were found to be resistant to vancomycin (Fig. 2) out of 20 isolates of *E. faecalis* obtained from chicken samples (40%). Molecular characterization of 20 enterococci isolates showed that all examined isolates were found to be positive for presence of Enterococcus 16S rRNA and *E. faecalis* 16S rRNA, while only 8 isolates were found to be positive for presence of *vanA gene* representative for Vancomycin resistant Enterococci (Fig. 3,4 and 5).

Table (3): The incidence rate of Enterococci in chicken flocks:

Chicken flocks (n= 12)	No. of examined samples	Positive	%
Broilers	100	13	13.0
Saso	100	16	16.0
Layers	100	17	17.0
Total	300	46	15.3

Fig. (1): Esculin hydrolysis by Enterococci Bile Esculin agar is indicated by a blackening of the media around the colonies.

Fig. (2): Results of Antibiotic Susceptibility Tests using Muller Hinton agar medium

Fig. (3): PCR products specific for Enterococcus 16S rRNA (337 bp). **Lane L:** 100 bp molecular weight DNA ladder with a size range of 100-1000 bp. **Lanes 1-20:** Positive isolates for presence of Enterococcus 16S rRNA. **Lane N:** Negative control

Fig. (4): PCR products specific for *E. fecalis* 16S rRNA (310 bp). **Lane L:** 100 bp molecular weight DNA ladder with a size range of 100-1000 bp. **Lanes 1-20:** Positive isolates for presence of *E. fecalis* 16S rRNA. **Lane N:** Negative control

Fig. (5): PCR products specific for *vanA* gene (885 bp). **Lane L:** 100 bp molecular weight DNA ladder with a size range of 100-1000 bp. **Lanes (2, 5, 6, 9, 14, 15, 16, 19):** Positive isolates for presence of *E. fecalis* 16S rRNA. **Lane N:** Negative control

Discussion

Enterococci are considered as opportunistic bacteria that can cause clinical diseases among human, poultry, and other species. *Enterococcus spp.* in commercial livestock and poultry could contaminate the food chains during processing or find their way into the environment. In this study, Enterococcus isolates from chicken flocks revealed typical phenotypic characteristics by the standard bacteriological technique.

The tabulated data in **Table (3)** showed that the prevalence rate of *Enterococcus spp.* from the chicken samples was 46% which was lower than that investigated by **Nowakiewicz et al., (2017)** who isolated *Enterococcus spp.* from chicken samples with percentage (87%) and **Diarra et al. (2010)** (72.8%). Also, the recorded data in **Table (3)** clarified that the isolation rate of enterococci from the examined chicken flocks was 13, 16 and 17% in broilers, sasso

and layers flocks, respectively. The difference of results may be due to difference of geographical areas, samples count and sampling techniques. The pattern of housing of poultry could affect the prevalence of *Enterococcus* spp. among chicken flocks. The most predominant isolated *Enterococcus* species among chicken samples was *E. faecalis*. This result was agreed to that reported by **Maasjost et al., (2015)** who found that the most isolated strain from the samples of various poultry showing clinical symptoms was predominance of *E. faecalis* and **Stępień-Pyśniak et al., (2016)** who isolated *E. faecalis* spp. from poultry farms with percentage (74.4%). In contrary, **Ruzauskas et al. (2009)** and **Diarra et al. (2010)** found that the most predominant strain was *E. faecium*. The causes of these differences in *Enterococcus* species distribution among chicken may be due to the variety of age and type of feed, housing, density, livestock, temperature, humidity, and antimicrobial agent usage. Genus-specific PCR primers to 16S rRNA have already been designed and found useful for distinguishing strains of *Enterococcus* spp. PCR amplification followed by sequencing and sequence comparison of target genes has also allowed differentiation of species of Enterococci. The phylogenetic analysis of the

sequences of the *Enterococcus* spp. is important to differentiate species particularly for the environmental isolates. Molecular detection of Enterococcus 16S rRNA was performed by PCR reactions for 20 confirmed isolates to Enterococci. The Enterococcus 16S rRNA was amplified at (337 bp) in 20 isolates as shown in **Fig. (3)**. Also, molecular detection of *E. faecalis* 16S rRNA was performed by PCR reactions for 20 confirmed isolates to *E. faecalis*. The *E. faecalis* 16S rRNA was amplified at (310 bp) in 20 isolates as shown in **Fig. (4)**. Antimicrobial resistance can involve not just obvious pathogens but also commensal bacteria, which may act as an enormous reservoir of antimicrobial resistance genes. Therefore, avian infections with antibiotic resistant enterococci could reservoirs and disseminators for MDR enterococci to humans. The antibiotic sensitivity results showed that among 20 isolates of *E. faecalis* obtained from chicken samples, 8 isolates were found to be resistant to vancomycin (40%). These results disagreed with **Stępień-Pyśniak et al., (2016)** who recorded that *Enterococcus* spp. were resistant vancomycin (0.11%). In addition, **Ruzauskas et al., (2009)** revealed that Enterococcus spp. were highly sensitive to vancomycin with percentage (100%). These results indicate

that the overuse of antibiotics and chemotherapeutic compounds in poultry production may lead to the population of multidrug resistant Enterococci in chicken. Moreover, Molecular detection of Vancomycin resistance gene A (*Van A*) was performed by PCR reactions for 20 confirmed isolates to *E. faecalis*. The *Van A* gene was amplified at (885 bp) in 8 isolates only as shown in **Fig., (5)**. These results were nearly related to **Hassan et al., (2008)** who revealed that *van A* was observed in (22.4%) of *E. faecalis* and overall *van A* detected in (36.4%) of poultry Enterococcus isolates. In conclusion, this study confirms that Enterococcus of chicken origin showed antibiotic resistance profile which indicating that chicken may be a reservoir of genes important for the pathogenic potential of human Enterococcus. The vancomycin resistant *E. faecalis* constitutes one of the most predominant Enterococcus species among chicken. Thus, the prevention and control programs of Enterococcus should be focused to control these species.

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